
Synthesis and Characterization of 1(4-Tolyl)-2(Phenyl thiocarbamido)-1-Ethanol

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Abstract:

Demand of active drugs molecules synthesis ceaselessly upsurges due to population growth rate. Present research scheme designed to synthesize 1(4-tolyl)-2(Phenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol by the interactions of 4-(2-amino-1-hydroxyethyl) toluene and phenyl isothiocyanate in acetone medium, to isolate 1(4-Tolyl)-2(Phenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol. The product thus synthesized in these reactions and characterized on the basis of conventional elemental analysis, chemical characteristics and through IR, PMR, CMR and Mass spectral analysis.

Keywords: 4-(2-amino-1-hydroxyethyl)toluene, phenyl isothiocyanate, 1(4-Tolyl)-2(Phenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol

Introduction:

Population of the world terribly growing along with that basic demands of health and medicine related things. World researchers were pointed their attention toward this aspect and working with challenge toward same. Pathogens are become resistive against existing some drugs moieties thus have a great need to developed more active and potent drugs moieties with good solubility, diffusion and activity that will be demonstrate effective pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetics of drugs. The literature survey divulges that from last couple of decades' numerous advances, theories and new concepts regarding to synthesis of novel moieties, chemical, physical as well as biological study of benzenoid and non-benzenoid, heteroacyclic and heterocyclic compounds were studied¹⁻⁵. These compounds have their

own identity and importance in the chemical and life sciences due to their variety of applications in medicinal, agricultural, pharmaceutical, industrial, biotechnological and biochemical sciences⁶⁻¹⁰. If we think about the drugs we can define the history of medicine by these compounds.

In the view of the utilities of these compounds in various fields and as a part of present research work, recently being undertaken in this laboratory in the synthesis of nitrogen, nitrogen and sulphur containing heteroacycles and heterocycles and to investigate their medicinal, pharmaceutical, agricultural, industrial, biotechnological and biochemical significance¹¹⁻¹⁸, hence interactions of 4-(2-amino-1-hydroxyethyl)chlorobenzene and p-tolylisothiocyanate in acetone medium, to isolate 1(4-Chlorophenyl)-2(p-Tolylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol.

Methods and Material:

All AR grade chemicals were used throughout experiment.

Synthesis of 1(4-Tolyl)-2(Phenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol:

1(4-Tolyl)-2(Phenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol was synthesized by refluxing 4-(2-amino-1-hydroxyethyl) toluene and Phenylisothiocyanate in acetone medium for 2 hours. After completion of reaction, to isolate 1(4-Tolyl)-2(Phenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol from solvent. After distillation of acetone the product is isolated which is recrystallized from ethanol to get white colour crystalline solid flakes with m.p. 82°C.

Result and Discussion:

Properties of 1(4-Tolyl)-2(phenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol:

The compound is white colour crystalline solid flakes, C₁₆H₁₉N₂S with m.p. 78°C. It gave positive test for nitrogen, chlorine and sulphur. Desulphurised with alkaline plumbite solution. Soluble in boiled sodium hydroxide, sulphuric acid, 1,4-dioxane, hydrochloric acid and nitric acid and was sparingly soluble in boiled water, ethanol, acetone and benzene. Formed picrates having melting point 95°C.

Elemental analysis (%): Found (Calculated) C- 70.81 (71.63), H-7.06 (7.20), N-10.32 (10.13), S-11.81 (11.40),

FTIR spectrum (ν cm⁻¹): The IR spectrum of compound was carried out in KBr pellets on SHIMADZU IR spectrometer¹⁹⁻²⁴.

2773. 64-2565.33 (Aliphatic C-H stretching), 2902.87 (Aromatic C-H stretching), 1945.82 (N-C=S stretching), 1589.99-1815.02 (C=N stretching), 1897.95 (C=S stretching), 3050.95 (Two N-H stretching), 3195.83 (Alcoholic O-H stretching), 1180.72-1244.50 (C-O stretching), 1505.55-1294.24 (Aliphatic -H bending), 1070.49-611.43 (Aromatic -H bending).

PMR spectrum data: The PMR spectrum of a compound was recorded in CDCl₃+DMSO_{d6} on Bruker Advance-II 400 NMR spectrometer^{19-20,25-28}. This spectrum distinctly displayed the signals, due to four aromatic protons in the range at δ 7.509 – δ 7.288 ppm of phenyl group, four aromatic protons in the range at δ 7.226 - δ 7.171 ppm, alcoholic -H at δ 3.652, two amino -NH protons at δ 9.7422 ppm, methyne (-CH) proton at δ 2.335, two diastereotopic methylene protons at δ 2.445 ppm and three methyl protons at δ 2.341.

Conclusion:

Recent obtained data from chemical characteristics, elemental and spectral analysis it is clear that the newly synthesized present compound was assigned the structure as 1(4-Tolyl)-2(Phenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol. This work create scope to studies various chemical, pharmaceutical, agricultural and biological applications of newly synthesized 1(4-Tolyl)-2(Phenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol.

1-(4-Tolyl)-2-(Phenylthiocarbamido)-1-ethanol

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